

Ventricular Septal Aneurysm Mimicking Sinus of Valsalva Aneurysm!

Celestine Odigwe, M.D.^a, Brent Ruiz, M.D.^a, Mohammad As Sayaideh, M.D.^a, Hajira Malik, M.D.^a,
Alexis Parks, D.O.^a, Sanchitha Nagaraj, M.D.^a, Mashal Mumtaz, M.D.^b,
Bassam Omar, M.D., Ph.D.^{a,c}, Christopher Malozzi, D.O.^a, Suganya Monoharan, M.D.^a

Description

The above 2-D transthoracic echocardiography (TTE) images (A – E) and axial computed tomography (CT) image (F) show a ventricular septal aneurysm (VSA). Image A is a parasternal short axis TTE frame across the aortic valve (AV). Aneurysmal outpouching is seen along the right coronary cusp (RCC) suspicious for a sinus of Valsalva aneurysm of the RCC. Color flow and continuous wave Doppler (green arrow) in image B, however, reveal that there is systolic, high velocity flow

across the aneurysm, consistent with a ventricular septal defect (VSD) with a VSA. Image C is an apical 4-chamber TTE view demonstrating the anatomic location of the VSA at the proximal ventricular septum, with high velocity systolic color flow Doppler (green arrow) shown across the VSD in image D. Further, parasternal long axis TTE image (E) and Axial CT with contrast image (F) confirm the location of the aneurysm at the proximal ventricular septum separate from the aortic valve.

Discussion

Ventricular septal defects (VSDs) may have variable locations, sizes and numbers, which can determine their physiologic significance and outcomes. While some may close spontaneously, especially small muscular VSDs, other large defects could result in pulmonary hypertension; infundibular obstruction and progressive aortic insufficiency if not properly evaluated and treated early [1].

Ventricular septal aneurysm (VSA) is uncommon; associated with about 19 % of VSDs [2]. It is often diagnosed incidentally by echocardiography or computed tomography and can be confused for a right ventricular mass [3]. Although it usually does not cause symptoms, cases of thromboembolism [4], obstruction of the right ventricular outflow tract [5], and electrical conduction abnormalities [6] have been reported.

Echocardiographic diagnosis of VSA can be challenging. As demonstrated in the above image, VSA can mimic a sinus of Valsalva aneurysm, especially in the short axis TTE views at the aortic valve level. The opposite has also been reported, whereby a sinus of Valsalva aneurysm associated with a VSD was mimicking a VSA [7].

Manuscript submitted March 3, accepted March 7, 2025
a Division of Cardiology. University of South Alabama,
Mobile, AL 36617

b Department of Internal Medicine, University
College of Medicine and Dentistry, Lahore, Pakistan

c Corresponding Author: Bassam Omar, Division of
Cardiology, University of South Alabama, 2451 USA
Medical Center Dr., Mobile, AL 36617, USA.

Email: bomar@health.southalabama.edu

<https://cardiofellows.com/newsletter-march-2025.html>

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KEYWORDS: Ventricular Septal Aneurysm; Ventricular Septal Defect; Congenital Heart Disease.

Reference this article as:

Odigwe C, Ruiz B, As Sayaideh M, Malik H, Parks A, Nagaraj S, Mumutaz M, Omar B, Malozzi C, Manoharan S. Ventricular Septal Aneurysm Mimicking Sinus of Valsalva Aneurysm! *Cardiofel Newslet* 2025. March; 8(3):6 – 7